

A DISCUSSION ABOUT SPECIAL RELATIVITY

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Abstract:

This article suggests an experiment to analyze a very long moving object. When one end of it emits a beam of light, we measure the time when the sensors located in different locations receive the light. Based on the theory of relativity (special relativity), when using different inertial frames of reference, the results become different after analysis. This is impossible because there must be a unique result in real physical world. This is also against one of the postulates of special relativity that the laws of physics are the same for all observers in any inertial frame of reference relative to one another. An additional analysis from a different angle also resulted in an impossible contradiction. Thus, the theory of relativity (Special Relativity) should be mistaken.

Key Words: Special Relativity, Theory of Relativity, Albert Einstein, Speed of Light, Frame of Reference, Theoretical Physics

Main Text:

An experiment is designed as follows:

As light travels 299792458 meters per second in vacuum, let's suppose, in the vacuum space, there is a very long and thin and rigid rod X whose length is 299792458 plus 1 meters = 299792459 meters. And there is another short rod Y whose length is 1 meter. Please see Figure 1.

Figure 1 (t_0)

Point A, point B, and point C are all located on the rod X, while point A is located at one end of the rod X, point B is located at another end of the rod X, point C is located one meter away from point B.

Rod X and rod Y are parallel to each other. And they are very near to each other. Their distance is one millimeter, as seen from Figure 1.

Point D and point E are located on the rod Y. Point D is located at one end of the rod Y and point E is located at another end of the rod Y. From point B to point A is the same direction as from point D to point E.

Relative to the rod Y, the rod X travels in vacuum space at the speed of 1 meter per second in the direction from point B to Point A. According to the theory of relativity (special relativity), the laws of physics are the same for all observers in any inertial frame of reference relative to one another (principle of relativity). Thus, we can also say, relative to the rod X, the rod Y travels in vacuum space at the speed of 1 meter per

second in the direction from point E to Point D. So, after 1 second, the relative position of the 2 rods will be like Figure 2.

Figure 2 (t_1)

And very accurate atomic clocks are put at each of the 5 points A, B, C, D, and E to measure the time when events happen.

Before we put the 5 clocks at the 5 points, the clocks are well synchronized. And because the rods travel at a very low relative speed, only one meter per second, the theory of relativity says that Time dilation effect can be neglectable, i.e., the 5 clocks will also be well synchronized although the rods are moving relative to each other. Because the rod travelling speed is so low, the theory of relativity also tells us that the effects of Length contraction and Relativity of simultaneity can be neglected during our analysis.

At point A we put a light source. At each point B, C, D, and E, we put a sensor to detect the light emitted by the light source at point A.

When the rod X travels relative to rod Y to the position where point D is side by side with point C, i.e., point D is 1 millimeter away from point C, as shown in Figure 1, the light source at point A emits a beam of light (we call this time as t_0). At this time t_0 , the clock at point A has a measurement of time (t_0). Then we will measure the time when this beam of light reach the sensors located at point B, C, D, and E.

According to the theory of relativity (special relativity), the speed of light in a vacuum is the same for all observers, regardless of their relative motion or of the motion of the light source. Then:

- according to the observer on the rod Y, rod X is moving, rod Y is static all the time, so:

when this beam of light is emitted (t_0), the source of light is 299792458 meters away from the sensor at point C. Because the rod travels at the speed of 1 meter per second, 1 second after the beam of light is emitted (we call this time as t_1 , whereas $t_1 - t_0 = 1$ second), the sensor at point B will 299792458 meters away from the position where the beam of light is emitted. At this time (t_1), point B travels to the position of point C when at t_0 and point D is side by side with point B, i.e., point D is 1 millimeter away from point B, as shown by Figure 2. Therefore, obviously, when the beam of light reaches the sensor at point B, the time measurement will be exactly 1 second. And apparently, when this beam of light reach the sensor located at point C, the measurements of time will be less than 1 second, i.e., $299792458/299792459 = 0.99999999666435905914498002766641$ second. This is true because when the beam of light has travelled for $299792458/299792459$ second, the distance it has travelled is $t \cdot v = 299792458/299792459 \cdot 299792458 = 299792458^2/299792459$ meters. So the light has travelled to the point $299792458^2/299792459$ meters away from the position where the beam of light is emitted. At the same time, after $299792458/299792459$ second, the sensor at point C has travelled $t \cdot v = 299792458/299792459 \cdot 1 = 299792458/299792459$ meters. Because $299792458^2/299792459 + 299792458/299792459 = 299792458$ meters, which is the original distance between point A and point C, so the light meets the sensor at point C when the measurement of the time is $299792458/299792459$ second.

At time t_1 , when point D is one millimeters away from point B and point C is one millimeters away from point E, we can know by simple calculation that this beam of light reach point D and point B almost at the same

